

Separation of Titanium from Zirconium, Hafnium, Thorium and related Elements with Aliquat 336S from Ascorbate Solutions

(Ms.) MANJUSHA A. KARVE and SHRIPAD M. KHOPKAR*

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Bombay-400 076

Manuscript received 23 November 1992, revised 9 July 1993, accepted 19 July 1993

Titanium(IV) was extracted at pH 4.5 from 0.01 M ascorbic acid with 0.1 M Aliquat 336S in xylene and was stripped with 1 M hydrochloric acid and determined spectrophotometrically as its complex with tiron at 380 nm. The group separation of Ti, Zr, Hf and Th was possible in any ratio. Titanium was also separated from Fe, Cr, Mo and V, which are generally associated with each other in real samples. The method was extended for the analysis of titanium in ilmenite. The method is simple, rapid, selective and reproducible with a relative standard deviation of 0.42%.

Titanium was extracted from thiocyanate media¹⁻³, hydroxamic acids⁴, xylene orange⁵, caffeic acid⁶ and chromotropic acid⁷, but none of them permitted group separations. However, from gallic⁸, malonic⁹, oxalic¹⁰, tartaric¹¹ and citric acid¹² good separations were possible. An attempt was made to use ascorbic acid¹³ for the separation of titanium from iron and aluminium with trioctyl methyl ammonium chloride, but the method was not selective. This paper presents systematic investigations for extraction of titanium with Aliquat 336 from ascorbate solution. The method permits sequential group separations.

Results and Discussion

Extraction of Ti as the function of pH :
The pH for the quantitative extraction of titanium(IV) was ascertained by extracting it between pH 1.0 and 8.0 with 4% solutions of various liquid anion exchangers in xylene. With Aliquat 336S extraction was quantitative at pH 2.0-7.5, whereas with Amberlite LA-1, Amberlite LA-2 and Primene JMT extraction was quantitative at pH 2.0-4.0 but trioctylamine was poor extractant. Since the extraction was quan-

titative with Aliquat 336 over a broad pH range, it was preferred.

Effect of varying concentration of Aliquat 336S :
Titanium(IV) was extracted at pH 4.5 with varying concentrations of Aliquat 336S with xylene as the diluent. The extraction was quantitative from 8.0×10^{-2} M Aliquat 336S. Therefore, 10×10^{-2} M Aliquat 336S was used.

Effect of varying concentration of ascorbic acid :
Titanium(IV) was extracted at pH 4.5 with 0.1 M Aliquat 336S in xylene from varying concentrations of ascorbic acid ranging from 1.0×10^{-3} to 10×10^{-3} M. With 9×10^{-3} M ascorbic acid extraction was complete. Hence 0.01 M ascorbic acid was used.

Effect of various diluents : Maintaining phase volume ratio of 1 : 1, different solvents such as benzene, toluene, xylene, hexane, cyclohexane, chloroform and carbon tetrachloride were tested as the diluent for Aliquat 336S. The extraction was found to be quantitative only with aromatic hydrocarbons. However, xylene was preferred as it was non-toxic in nature and produced emulsion-free clear phases.

*Present address : Department of Chemical Technology, University of Bombay, Matunga, Bombay-400 019.

Period of equilibration : Separate extraction studies of titanium were performed with varying period of shaking, i.e. 1, 2, 3, 5, 7 and 10 min. The corresponding extent of extractions were 95.0, 96.0, 99.6, 99.6, 99.6 and 99.4 respectively. A 5 min period of equilibration was quite adequate for the quantitative extraction.

Effect of various stripping agents : Titanium(IV) after extraction was stripped with various mineral acids or corresponding salts. The stripping was quantitative with hydrochloric (1.0–8.0 M), nitric (1.0–6.0 M), sulphuric (0.5–6.0 M), hydrobromic (1.0–5.0 M) acids or with sodium nitrate (1.0–2.0 M) and ammonium hydroxide (1.0 M). The stripping was also studied with a mixture of sulphuric acid and hydrogen peroxide. It was quantitative with 0.1 M sulphuric acid containing 3% hydrogen peroxide. 1 M hydrochloric acid was preferred as the stripping agent as it facilitated direct spectrophotometric determination of titanium with tiron.

Nature of extracted species : The composition of the extracted species was ascertained by plotting graph of $\log D$ against \log of Aliquat 336S concentration at a fixed pH and ascorbic acid concentration, and graph of $\log D$ against \log of ascorbic acid concentration at a fixed pH and Aliquat 336S concentration. The corresponding slopes were 1.73 and 2.7 respectively. Hence, the nature of extracted species was $[(R_4N)_2Ti(asc)_3]$. This ratio is in agreement with similar extractions from mineral acid solutions¹⁴.

Separation of titanium(IV) from binary mixtures : Titanium(IV) (40 μ g) was extracted in the presence of other ions. The tolerance limit was set as the amount of foreign ion required to cause $\pm 2\%$ error in the recovery of titanium. The alkali, alkaline earths, Al, Tl^{III}, Pb, Y, Ta, Mn, Fe^{III}, Co, Ni and Cu^{II} were not extracted with titanium and were therefore separated in ratios of 1 : 50, while Ga, In and Mo were co-extracted with titanium. Titanium was first stripped with 6 M hydrochloric acid while

all these remaining elements were stripped with 1 M nitric acid. Similarly, Sc, Th, V and Nb were also co-extracted with titanium, therefore titanium was first stripped with 0.1 M sulphuric acid containing 3% hydrogen peroxide while other metals were stripped with 1 M hydrochloric or nitric acid.

Separation from multi-component mixtures : The separation of titanium from different multi-component mixtures is shown in Table 1. As indicated in this table the reagents are added in successive order for sequential separation of ions in the various mixtures.

Group separation of Ti^{IV}, Th^{IV}, Zr^{IV} and Hf^{IV} : A mixture of Ti, Zr, Hf and Th was separated after extraction by stripping titanium with 0.1 M sulphuric acid containing 3% hydrogen peroxide then Th with 0.5 M sulphuric acid, Hf with 9 M hydrochloric acid and finally Zr with 2 M hydrochloric acid. The metal after stripping were determined after dry ashing by spectrophotometry with suitable chromogenic ligands.

Analysis of real sample : Illeminite (~ 0.5 g) was fused with potassium pyrosulphate (5 g). The fused melt was dissolved in 20% sulphuric acid (10 ml), then filtered and diluted to 100 ml with distilled water¹⁵. An aliquot of this solution was taken and titanium was extracted as per the general procedure. The amount of titanium found was 31.0% against the standard value of 31.6%.

The proposed method is simple and rapid and selective. It is useful for the separation of titanium from Fe, Mo, Cr, V and Nb which are present in steel. The method is reproducible with a relative standard deviation of 0.42%.

Experimental

An ECIL G-8866C spectrophotometer with matched 10 mm corex glass cuvette and an ECIL pH meter were used.

TABLE 1—SEPARATION OF TITANIUM(IV) FROM MULTICOMPONENT MIXTURES

Sl. no.	Metal ion	Amount taken μg	Amount found μg	Stripping agent <i>M</i>	Recovery %	Chromogenic ligand	λ_{\max} nm
1.	Ti ^{IV}	40	39.8	0.5 H ₂ SO ₄	99.6	Tiron	380
	Zr ^{IV}	20	19.7	9 HCl	98.6	Arsenazo III	650
	Hf ^{IV}	40	39.6	2 HCl	99.1	Xylenol orange	540
2.	Ti ^{IV}	40	39.8	0.1 H ₂ SO ₄ + 3% H ₂ O ₂	99.6	Tiron	380
	Th ^{IV}	80	79.5	6 HCl	99.5	Arsenazo III	650
	U ^{VI}	100	99.6	0.5 NaOH	99.6	Tiron	665
3.	Ti ^{IV}	40	39.8	6 HCl	99.6	Tiron	380
	Mo ^{IV}	100	99.5	1 HNO ₃	99.5	Tiron	390
	Cr ^{IV}	100	99.6	Unextracted	99.6	Sym diphenyl-carbazide	570
4.	Ti ^{IV}	80	79.5	0.1 H ₂ SO ₄ + 3% H ₂ O ₂	99.4	Tiron	380
	V ^{IV}	40	39.8	1 HCl	99.5	AAS	318.4
	Ni ^{II}	80	79.6	Unextracted	99.6	PAR	510
5.	Ti ^{VI}	40	39.8	6 HCl	99.6	Tiron	380
	In	100	99.6	1 HNO ₃	99.6	PAR	510
	Al ^{III}	100	99.6	Unextracted	99.6	Alizarin Red S	510
6.	Ti ^{IV}	20	19.8	0.1 H ₂ SO ₄ + 3% H ₂ O ₂	99.0	Tiron	380
	Th ^{IV}	20	19.9	0.5 H ₂ SO ₄	99.5	Arsenazo III	650
	Hf ^{IV}	20	19.6	9 HCl	98.0	Arsenazo III	650
	Zr ^{IV}	20	19.6	2 HCl	98.0	Xylenol orange	540
7.	Ti ^{IV}	20	19.8	0.1 H ₂ SO ₄ +3%H ₂ O ₂	99.0	Tiron	380
	Th ^{IV}	80	79.6	0.5 H ₂ SO ₄	99.5	Arsenazo III	650
	Hf ^{IV}	40	39.6	9 HCl	99.0	Arsenazo III	650
	Zr ^{IV}	60	59.4	2 HCl	99.1	Xylenol orange	540
8.	Ti ^{IV}	80	79.6	0.1 H ₂ SO ₄ + 3% H ₂ O ₂	99.6	Tiron	380
	Th ^{IV}	20	19.8	0.5 H ₂ SO ₄	99.0	Arsenazo III	650
	Hf ^{IV}	40	39.6	9 HCl	99.1	Arsenazo III	650
	Zr ^{IV}	60	59.5	2 HCl	99.2	Xylenol orange	540

A stock solution of titanium(IV) was prepared by dissolving titanium metal (0.1 g) in 1 *M* H₂SO₄ containing a drop of HF. The solution was diluted to 100 ml with distilled water and standardised gravimetrically with cupferron¹⁶; it contained 1 mg ml⁻¹ of Ti. A diluted solution containing 40 mg ml⁻¹ of Ti was prepared by appropriate dilution which had pH ~ 4.0.

Aliquat 336S (tricapryl monomethyl ammonium chloride; General Mills Ltd., U.S.A.), Amberlite LA-1 (*N*-diodecyl(trialkyl)amine), Amberlite LA-2 (*N*-lauryl(trialkyl)amine), Primene JMT (a primary amine with C₁₂-C₁₈ carbon; Rohm and Hass, U.S.A.) and TOA (trioctylamine; Riedel, Germany) were used without further purification.

They were converted into the ascorbate form as usual¹⁷. Tiron(disodium-1,2-dihydroxy benzene-3,5-disulphon) was used as a 2% aqueous solution. The buffer solution (pH 4.7) was prepared by mixing equal volumes of 1 *M* acetic acid and 1 *M* sodium acetate.

General procedure : To an aliquot of solution containing titanium (40 μg) 0.01 *M* ascorbic acid was added. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 4.5 (if necessary). The solution was diluted to 10 ml with distilled water. Then 0.1 *M* Aliquat 336S (10 ml) in xylene was added to it. It was shaken on a wrist action flask shaker for 5 min. The two phases were allowed to settle and separate. The titanium

from the organic phase was stripped with 1 M HCl. To the evaporated phase, water (5 ml), 0.5% tiron (2 ml), 0.1 M ammonium hydroxide (1 ml) and ammonium acetate buffer of pH 4.7 (5 ml) were added. The solution was made upto 25 ml with distilled water. The absorbance of the yellow coloured complex was measured at 380 nm against a reagent blank.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for sponsoring this project and awarding a Fellowship to one of the authors (M.A.K.).

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